

Efficient on-board quantization and data reduction methods for present and next-generation SAR systems: recent advances and future perspectives

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Knowledge for Tomorrow

Outline

- Introduction and motivation
- Efficient quantization for multi-channel SAR
- Linear predictive coding for staggered SAR
- Block-frequency data compression for FScan systems
- Performance-optimized quantization for SAR and InSAR applications
- Conclusions and outlook

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Introduction and Motivation

- Next-generation spaceborne SAR missions
 - **Large data rates required:** multiple channels, large PRF/bandwidths...
 - Harder requirements for: **Onboard memory**
Downlink capacity

- **Quantization** of SAR raw data affects
 - **Amount of data** to be handled
 - **Quality** of the SAR products

- **Efficient resource allocation** for future missions
 - Design **feasibility**
 - **Performance** aligned with requirements

Block Adaptive Quantization (BAQ) for SAR Systems

- **BAQ** uses local statistics of raw data blocks (128 range samples) to set the decision levels (Δ)
- For SAR applications, typical BAQ rates between **2 and 6 bits/sample**
- Quantization as AWGN source holds for homogeneous targets
- BAQ adapts to the space-varying dynamic range of SAR data

Impact of Quantization on Interferometric SAR Performance

Phase Errors for 2-bit BAQ

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Limitations of Conventional (Single-Channel) SAR

Wide swath width ← **PRF** → **Fine azimuth resolution**

TerraSAR-X	ScanSAR	Stripmap	Spotlight
Azimuth Res. δ_a	16 m	3 m	1 m
Swath Width, W_g	100 km	30 km	10 km

Data Reduction for Multi-Channel SAR

$PRF_{eff} > PBW$

↓

Correlation/redundancy among azimuth samples

↓

**Proposed MC-BAQ:
joint DFT and variable bit allocation**

Sentinel NG

Az. Resolution, δ_a	1.2 m
Swath Width, W_g	100 km

Simulations – Homogeneous Target, SQNR

Simulations – Backscatter Inhomogeneities, SQNR

Martone et al., *Efficient onboard quantization for multi-channel SAR systems*, GRSL 2019.

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Staggered SAR for HRWS – Tandem-L

- DLR proposal for bistatic, fully polarimetric L-band InSAR mission
- Goal: monitoring of dynamic Earth processes: **bio-**, **geo-**, **idro-**, and **cryo-**sphere
- PRI variation combined with digital beamforming (DBF) in elevation

M. Villano, Staggered SAR, PhD Thesis, 2017.

Linear Predictive Coding for Staggered SAR

Azimuth oversampling: exploit **correlation** to **reduce** the signal **dynamic**

$$\text{Prediction Gain } G_{NP} = \frac{\sigma_x^2}{\sigma_d^2}$$

Simulations – Homogeneous Target, SQNR

A-priori knowledge of **gaps position**: optimize **bit rate** allocation and **prediction order**

Martone et al., Predictive quantization for data volume reduction in staggered SAR systems, TGRS 2020.

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Frequency Scan (FScan) for HRWS – Acquisition Principle

- FScan: a low-complexity alternative to the Scan On Receive (SCORE).
- Wide swath illuminated with a **continuously changing center frequency**
- In reception, swath recorded within a **shorter time window** (EWL).
- The information of the targets is **separable in frequency**.

	Resolution	Swath
TerraSAR-X	3 m	30 km
FScan	1 m	80 km

C. Roemer *et. al.*, *Frequency Scanning applied to Wide Area SAR Imaging*, EUSAR 2018.

Time-Frequency Diagrams

Block-Frequency Quantization for Fscan SAR

Parameter	Value
Center frequency, f_0	9.8 GHz
Transmit bandwidth, B_{TX}	1200 MHz
Target bandwidth, B_{img}	300 MHz
Orbit height, h_{sat}	514 km
Number of azimuth channels, N_{az}	4
Azimuth resolution, δ_{az}	1 m

For each raw data range line:

- Subdivision in blocks & DFT
- Discard not informative samples
- Downlink of quantized DFT coefficients

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Quantization Effects and Backscatter

Iowa (USA) – Agricultural, homogeneous

Phase Error ($\Delta\phi$)

Mexico City – large dynamic range

Phase Error ($\Delta\phi$)

1. Cartesian quantizer (I/Q) → Low-amplitude signals more distorted
2. BAQ adapts to local signal statistics → “masking” effect

Quantization as non-linear signal-dependent error source

Performance-Optimized Block-Adaptive Quantization (PO-BAQ)

Test Site	σ_{σ^0}	bps for $\sigma_{\Delta\theta} = 5^\circ$	bps for $\sigma_{\Delta\theta} = 10^\circ$
Greenland - snow & ice, flat	Homogeneous		
Iowa (USA) - agricultural, flat	6.1 dB	3.5 bps	2.1 bps
Rondonia (Brazil) - rainforest, flat	6.6 dB	3.6 bps	2.5 bps
Death Valley (USA) - soil & rock, mountainous	7.0 dB	4.4 bps	2.8 bps
Las Vegas - urban, flat	7.4 dB	5.1 bps	3.5 bps
Mexico City - urban, mountainous	8.1 dB	5.6 bps	3.8 bps
Malaysia - tropical forest, mountainous	Heterogeneous		

Joint optimization of data rate and performance through apriori knowledge of backscatter

PO-BAQ – Example for Global Bit-Rate Allocation

Global bitrate map resulting from an InSAR phase error requirement $\sigma_{\Delta\varphi_q} = 5^\circ$.

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Summary

TC for MAC SAR

LPC for Staggered SAR

Block-Frequency for FScan

Performance-Optimized Quantization

Outlook

- Investigations of alternative data transformation and compression techniques (non-causal/non-linear prediction filters in combination with vector quantization...).
- Potentials of AI/DL-based approaches for SAR data compression, possibly in combination with efficient on-board processing solutions.
 - EU Horizon Project “**Smart On-board Processing for Earth Observation Systems (SOPHOS) with academic/research and industrial partners, KO Nov. 2022**

Summary

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Thanks for your attention!

